

Australian Research Data Landscape

An issues paper for the NRI Advisory Group

ARDC Senior Leadership Team, 22/8/2024

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Executive Summary

Context

The NDRI Strategy lists a number of desired outcomes. This document is focussed on the issues most pertinent to Outcome #3: Consistent in its standards for data collection, curation and access.

The Australian data storage environment is complex and fragmented and needs to be considered as an ecosystem of actors and service providers. Digital data can, and are, being stored in a wide range of locations. These are used variously according to disciplinary (usually internationally disciplinary) norms, researcher awareness, point in the research lifecycle at which the data is being processed, funder requirements, and the like.

The NDRIS recognises that Australia requires ‘... a sector-wide data management framework that considers the entire data lifecycle from creation to deletion and includes clear metadata and access standards.’ Indeed, every one of the outcomes listed in the NDRIS consultation draft will require a comprehensive national data management framework to deliver their desired outcomes.

Purpose

The purpose of this document is to outline the key concepts that need to be considered in the design of such a framework, describe some of the challenges facing any response to Outcome #3, and provide some recommendations.

Concepts

Research data includes both the data produced from research and the data that can be used for research. It should be viewed through two distinct lenses.

One is the data content itself, which will have potentially enduring value, and should be viewed as infrastructure in and of itself. Data content NDRI needs to address issues of governance, content and metadata standards, access controls, use of persistent identifiers, dataset collection development approaches, connections to analytics infrastructure, and the need to undertake an archival review process to make informed retention decisions. These are issues that are independent of how/where the data are stored.

The other is the technology used as data containers. Data Container NDRI needs to consider capacity planning, Trust and Identity capabilities (authentication and authorisation mechanisms), automation, investment in technology refresh and data migration over time, appropriate selection of storage technologies, and the interactions with system aspects such as the need for secure storage or connections to HPC. These are issues that need to be informed by the kinds of research data content that is being managed.

Both data content and data containers need to be in scope for the NDRI Strategy and will require different implementation considerations. The data management framework will need to address issues of what research data needs to be stored for the long-term, how this needs to be described, where it is going to be stored, and who will pay. Responsibility for data content will need to move between data creators, institutions, and data archives

over the course of research project lifecycles, and the costs for the associated data containers will need to be met at each stage.

Challenges

Data volumes continue to grow

Research data holdings at Australian research institutions are estimated to be c. 660 Petabytes by the end of 2024, with a compound annual growth rate of 22%. The equivalent figure for data intensive national facilities is not known. Work undertaken through the ARDC Data Retention and Institutional Underpinnings programs has examined data volume changes over the lifecycle of a notional research project and identified opportunities to reduce the data volumes retained. A number of the NRIs and NCRIS facilities are significant generators of data, and this is likely to increase.

Technology alone is not the solution

While data volumes continue to grow, increases in storage density and decreases in storage cost are slowing down. This means there is no technological silver bullet on the infrastructure side, and the NDRI Strategy will need to consider approaches to both data retention and data disposal - without this, the costs of data storage will continue to grow. The data management framework proposed in Outcome 3 will need to emphasise issues of what research data needs to be stored for the long-term, how this needs to be described, and where it is going to be stored. One way of addressing this is through a data storage and preservation framework as a sub-component of the overall data management framework. This will need to respond to current practice across the Australian research producing sector, as well as what is current practice for non-institutional holders of data that could be used by researchers (such as government or industry data). Clear guidance for researchers and institutions on what to store, when, and for how long it will be essential.

Institutions are key players

Institutions currently hold large volumes of research data, but need to deal with a wide range of disciplines. They hold the majority of data arising from research, but are facing increasing cost pressures from the lack of guidance on data retention and changing cost models from their storage providers. Unlike in the UK or Europe, there are few discipline-specific repositories in Australia that could help. A possible hybrid approach could involve a federated model for disciplinary support across the university sector, but this would require careful coordination.

Research is an inherently international activity

The NDRI Strategy will need to consider how best to integrate Australian investments in digital research infrastructure into their international context. In particular, the strategy will need to be based on careful consideration of how to embed international DRI best practice into Australian service delivery, how to contribute to and empower international DRI developments in areas that are strategic for Australia, how to expand and strengthen international networks for national and regional benefit, and how to enhance Australia's international DRI reputation through engagement and delivery.

Standards will be critical

Any sector-wide data management framework should be based on existing standards and frameworks. These might be generic standards such as Datacite metadata for DOIs or schema.org for discovery, or they might be more detailed community scientific standards such as FAIR implementation profiles.

Recommendations

- Coordinate a coherent approach to the research data ecosystem as a whole
- Embed an explicit data storage and preservation framework within the wider data management framework
- Provide guidance on application of the above framework to achieve a reduction in retained data volumes across NRI and NCRIS facilities
- Invest in data storage that build on the strengths of institutional, thematic, and discipline approaches
- Guide investments into retention of datasets of national significance that are likely to see high re-use
- Provide clearer guidance for how data generators could be more consistent in their standards for data collection, curation and access, as well as how to comply with FAIR and CARE data principles
- Provide clear guidance to researchers on what to store, when, and for how long
- Integrate Australian investments in digital research infrastructure into their international context

Context

The Australian data storage environment is complex and fragmented and needs to be considered as an ecosystem of actors and service providers. The diagram below only addresses the storage piece. It doesn't address the range of data generators and non-research actors/service providers.

Digital data¹ can, and are, being stored in a range of locations:

- Individual researcher-controlled local storage (laptop, PC, USB drives, thumb drives)
- Individual researcher-controlled cloud storage (OneDrive, Google Drive, Dropbox, etc)
- Laboratory storage (NAS, instrument-attached storage)
- Institutional storage (shared file systems, storage attached to local cloud/Tier 2 compute, data repositories, local Figshare instances)
- National storage (Nectar cloud storage, state-based eResearch nodes, HPC-associated storage, NCRIS data-intensive capabilities (operators of data generating instruments, data collecting sensor networks, data aggregators), Synchrotron, discipline archives such as LDaCA, ADA or AADC, government agencies such as GA, commercial cloud such as AWS or Azure)
- Discipline storage, often overseas (Pangea, Dryad)
- International storage (Zenodo, Figshare, journal repositories)

Figure 1: Visualising NDRI storage options

¹ The situation is even more complex when it comes to non-digital data, but this is currently out of scope for NDRI

These can be visualised as sitting on two axes: local provision through to global provision, and heterogeneous research objects to intentional public collections (Fig. 1). These locations are used variously according to disciplinary (usually internationally disciplinary) norms, researcher awareness, point in the research lifecycle at which the data is being processed, funder requirements, and the like. The NDRI Strategy will need to recognise the complexity of this ecosystem, and the nuances in how it is used, when making any investment decisions. In particular, the Strategy should aim to maximise the investments being made by existing ecosystem providers through national coordination activity.

Concepts

What are research data?

Research data are often defined as the data that is generated from research. However, this neglects a range of data sources that are potentially useful for research. These include data collected and managed by government, holdings in the cultural collections sector, and data collected by citizen scientists. For these reasons, research data should be regarded as both data from and data for research.

Data contents and data containers

It is useful to distinguish between the **research data contents** (and their associated metadata) and the **research data containers** (that is, the storage infrastructures and associated software) that hold them². The data contents will have potentially enduring value (particularly if they are observations at a point in time that cannot be remade), whereas the data container technologies will need to regularly be replaced. The NDRI strategy will need to respond to this critical distinction because each has separate stakeholders and concerns.

Data content NDRI needs to address issues of governance, content and metadata standards, access controls, use of persistent identifiers, dataset collection development approaches, connections to analytics infrastructure, and the need to undertake an archival review process to make informed retention decisions. These are issues that are independent of how/where the data are stored.

Data container NDRI needs to consider capacity planning, Trust and Identity capabilities (e.g. authentication and authorisation mechanisms and policies), automation, investment in technology refresh and data migration over time, appropriate selection of storage technologies, and the interactions with system aspects such as the need for secure storage or connections to HPC. These are issues that need to be informed by the kinds of research data content that is being managed.

Both data content and data containers need to be in scope for the NDRI Strategy.

² For more on this, see John Perry Barlow (2019), *Selling Wine Without Bottles: The Economy of Mind on the Global Net*, 18 *Duke Law & Technology Review* 8-31. <https://www.eff.org/pages/selling-wine-without-bottles-economy-mind-global-net>

In use vs at rest

Another distinction that is often made is between **data in use** and **data at rest**. The former applies during the active research phase, and the latter once the research is published. Of course, it is then possible for data to move back into active use later as part of new research activity. This distinction has implications for the underlying storage hardware design (e.g. the possibility of cheaper solutions for data at rest) and emphasises the requirement for archival decision-making capability across the board.

Lifecycles

The ARDC has been working with a number of Australian research institutions through the [Data Retention Program](#) (DRP), the [Institutional Underpinnings Program](#), and the associated [Research Data Culture Conversation](#) (RDCC) to better understand the issues around data storage. The Institutional Underpinnings program generated a report³ looking at the issues around data retention and disposal. This took a conventional research data lifecycle which had been developed as part of the ARDC Research Data Management Framework for Institutions⁴ and used it to provide a project-centric lifecycle perspective which was overlaid with notional data volume changes over the duration of the project (see Fig. 2⁵).

³ Jung, D., Haythornthwaite, A., Mertin, A., Lynn, H., Wilkinson, J. M., Burton, N., Soo, A.-L., Francis, R., Stevens, F., Cho, K. L. (Jacky) ., & Betbeder-Matibet, L. (2023). Retention and Disposal of Research Data: from current to best practices. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076891>

⁴ ARDC (2023). Research data management framework for institutions (Version 2). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8433246>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076895>

Figure 2: Research data lifecycle stages and notional data volumes

This view of the research data lifecycle, although coming from an institutional perspective, is relevant to the national research data ecosystem. Responsibility for that data content will need to move between data creators, institutions and data archives over the course of the lifecycle, and the costs for the associated data containers will need to be met at each stage. NDRI Strategy should aim to produce a data volume reduction curve across its own facilities and coordinate a coherent approach across the Figure 2 ecosystem as a whole, one that supports collaboration across NRI and the ongoing preservation of nationally significant datasets.

Challenges

Data volumes continue to grow

The joint work referenced above on data storage estimated that Australian research institutions at the end of 2021 were storing ~300PB of digital research content (based on what was stored by five RDCC units and extrapolating out)⁶. Of this, ~90PB was available for open discovery, and a further ~85PB was classed as sensitive.

⁶ Soo, Ai-Lin; Quenette, Steve; Francis, Rhys (2022): Research Data Culture Conversation - A Macro View of Retained Australian Academic Research Data. Monash University. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26180/20235570>

Work undertaken by the RDCC in 2023 estimated a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) in research data of 22% for data holdings by Australian research institutions⁷. This would suggest a figure of 659PB by the end of 2024.

At present there is no good estimate for the growth rate at data-intensive national facilities (such as NCI, Pawsey, CSIRO, ALA, IMOS, BPA) nor at international disciplinary repositories, but it is unlikely to be much less. It would be good to build on the work of the RDCC and DRP to derive a more accurate picture of the current holdings, relative proportions in use/at rest, growth rates for both, and what proportion is being managed through an archival framework.

And NRIs are contributors

A number of the NRIs and NCRIS facilities are significant generators of data. This might be from observations, from analyses, and from computation output. There is no consistent approach across these facilities to how they deal with data, and no visibility into their compliance with FAIR or CARE data principles.

The Strategy should provide clearer requirements on how data generators could be more consistent in their standards for data collection, curation and access. This would include the need for better capture of descriptive metadata at source based on agreed community standards, use of common data models, adoption of agreed vocabularies for semantic information, consistent use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) and alignment with the national PIDs strategy for research objects, instruments, organisations and individuals, and integration into appropriate discovery mechanisms. These should be required for data generated by NCRIS-funded instruments. The policy recommendations in the recently released WorldFair Policy Brief⁸ should also be considered as candidate requirements. Recommendations 1: Data Engineering, 2: Metadata uplift, 4: Reproducible and transparent research, and 8: Invest in Research Infrastructures are particularly relevant in this context.

The RDCC work made some assertions about the role of NRIs⁹ in data generation, but these would need to be validated against current practice. In particular, the NDRI Strategy implementation should be informed by a careful analysis of how the different categories of NRIs and individual NRIs are dealing with the data they collect/generate.

Technology alone is not the solution

At the same time that data continues to grow, increases in storage density (and a corresponding reduction in \$/TB) are tapering off¹⁰. This means that there is no magic technical solution on the horizon, despite the claims of some storage vendors, and archival media is not a good business to be in¹¹. There are new technologies under development (DNA, laser-silicon) but “history suggests it will be decades before these technologies impact the

⁷ Soo, Ai-Lin; FRANCIS, RHYS (2023). A First Macro View of Australian Retained Research Data. Monash University. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26180/22776320>

⁸ Hodson, S., & Gregory, A. (2024). WorldFAIR (D1.4) Second Policy Brief (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11242702>

⁹ Soo, Ai-Lin; FRANCIS, RHYS (2023). A First Macro View of Australian Retained Research Data. Monash University. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26180/22776320>

¹⁰ <https://blog.dshr.org/2023/06/2023-storage-roundup.html>

¹¹ <https://blog.dshr.org/2018/03/archival-media-not-good-business.html>

storage market”¹². This means that the data container side of the picture will not be the solution to the growth in storage requirements, and the Strategy needs to look at data content-side solutions, in particular coordinated approaches to data retention and disposal through an archival framework, as well as clearer guidance for researchers. This latter approach is one of the critical components in digital literacy training, and must also be included in NDRI training frameworks for researchers.

While networks continue to grow in capacity, the growth in data being generated and captured is growing more quickly. The AARNet 2022 annual report¹³ states that Member telecommunications traffic in 2022 grew 22% higher than 2021 and Non-Member traffic growth was 18%. This compares with the estimated 30% CAGR for data reported above. In addition, some of the datasets being managed are so large that moving the data to a compute location for analysis is not possible on a reasonable timescale. It is now more efficient to move the compute to the data (and containerisation technologies are making this much more feasible). Of course, major HPC facilities such as NCI and Pawsey will continue to be holders and processors of large data sets, but moving everything to these centres is not a feasible solution.

In addition to network bandwidth, a number of other issues may constrain the ability to move data. These include jurisdictional legal silos (particularly when moving health data across state boundaries), cybersecurity mandates, privacy concerns, institutional ethics requirements, and researcher or participant trust boundaries. A move towards greater use of common data models and federated (including privacy-preserving) analysis approaches offers a way forward. A recently constituted European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Taskforce looking at issues of Long-Term Data Retention is something that Australia should be tracking.

Institutions are key players

Institutions are the employers of the researchers who are generating the data. They are able to put in place policies to guide researchers, and also have the infrastructure base to offer data repository solutions. However these solutions are of necessity generalist ones. While they do hold some of the information that is required for good curation and archival decision making, they have limited ability to curate for the most effective disciplinary reuse.

The ARDC Institutional Underpinnings extension project looking at data retention and disposal produced a report¹⁴ with an analysis of 5 large universities and a series of recommendations for institutions covering data retention and disposal policies, roles and responsibilities, greater integration and automation of institutional systems, researcher engagement approaches, and the fostering of communities of practice.

This work should be extended into an agreed national archival framework that responds to current practice across the Australian research producing sector, as well as what is current practice for non-institutional holders of data that could be used by researchers (such as government or industry data). Such a framework would also need to address retention/disposal decisions made as data is moved between the locations in Figure 1. Without a

¹² <https://blog.dshr.org/2024/03/microsofts-archival-storage-research.html>

¹³ <https://www.aarnet.edu.au/uploads/resources/AARNet-Annual-Report-2022.pdf>

¹⁴ Jung, D., Haythornthwaite, A., Mertin, A., Lynn, H., Wilkinson, J. M., Burton, N., Soo, A.-L., Francis, R., Stevens, F., Cho, K. L. (Jacky) ., & Betbeder-Matibet, L. (2023). Retention and Disposal of Research Data: from current to best practices. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076891>

nationally agreed approach to data retention and disposal through an archival framework, the ecosystem in Fig. 1 will not produce the required diminution in data storage requirements.

Disciplinary approaches to research data storage and retention are able to focus on the needs of their discipline, and potentially maintain a team of data curation specialists with the required breadth of coverage. For instance in the UK a network of discipline-specific data centres provides specialised solutions. Discipline approaches are also able to use discipline best practice to inform appropriate archival decision making. And yet “disciplines” are typically loose associations of academics and don’t have the same sustainable enterprise resourcing to operate ongoing storage solutions like institutions. Behind most “discipline repositories” are usually a number of committed institutions.

The RDCC considered a model where institutions could come together in a federated model for disciplinary support, so that no one institution was responsible for supporting a discipline (of course, institutions would need to be incentivised to offer storage on behalf of researchers they do not employ, but this could be recast as them taking a national position as leaders in an area of strategic research strength).

The NDRI Strategy should put in place arrangements that build on the strengths of both approaches. The RDCC model is one such.

Nationally significant datasets require special attention from the NRI system, because these naturally span both institutional and disciplinary boundaries. They are national assets that support leading edge research and need intentional resourcing and preservation.

Data Security Issues

Research data has associated risks at rest, in use, and in transit. And all the risks below occur within changing compliance requirements and across a range of providers. A coordinated conversation (better yet, an actual coordinated approach) should be fundamental to any discussion around data collection, curation and access. Risks at rest include the potential for data breaches, the need to ensure data integrity over the long-term (which may require explicit migration and regular validation steps), and evolving regulatory regimes. Nationally significant datasets that are not open access, or have data that is anything above public, will automatically inherit / infer data security and/or governance requirements and related risks that need to be understood by institutions.

Risk in use include inappropriate access, data being combined in ways that reveal obfuscated elements, or data being moved outside of secure environments.

Risks in transit involve specific security issues that need to be considered and may also constrain what data can be moved to where and how.

Research is an inherently international activity

Because of the international nature of research, data collections that can be aggregated across national boundaries will give the scientific method the greatest statistical power and broadest analytic relevance. International infrastructure however suffers from the same sustainable resourcing challenges noted for disciplines above. For example, long standing international data infrastructure in the life sciences such as the Protein Data Bank (PDB) had previously been borne by big funding institutions such as NIH. The Global Biodata

Coalition is an international coalition of biomedical research who have recognised that the sustainable future for international infrastructure is through a federation of nationally funded institutionally backed data assets¹⁵.

The NDRI Strategy will need to consider how best to integrate Australian investments in digital research infrastructure into their international context. This is a nuanced issue. On the one hand, Australia can't do everything and investing in the use of overseas infrastructure is sometimes the cost-effective choice, assuming there are no legal/IP impediments to doing so. On the other hand, our commitment to investing in infrastructure buys us a seat at the decision-making table.

The strategy here will need to be based on careful consideration of how to embed international DRI best practice into Australian service delivery, how to contribute to and empower international DRI developments in areas that are strategic for Australia, how to expand and strengthen international networks for national and regional benefit, and how to enhance Australia's international DRI reputation through engagement and delivery.

Standards will be critical

In thinking about how to construct such a framework, it is important to recognise that this should be based on existing standards and frameworks. These might be generic standards such as Datacite metadata for DOIs or schema.org for discovery, or they might be more detailed community scientific standards such as FAIR implementation profiles.

Recommendations

In conclusion, the ARDC therefore believes that the NDRI Strategy should:

- Coordinate a coherent approach to the research data ecosystem as a whole
- Embed an explicit data storage and preservation framework within the wider data management framework
- Provide guidance on its application that leads to reduction in retained data volumes across NRI and NCRIS facilities
- Resource investments in data storage that build on the strengths of institutional, thematic, and discipline approaches
- Guide investments into retention of datasets of national significance that are likely to see high re-use
- Provide clearer guidance for how data generators could be more consistent in their standards for data collection, curation and access, as well as how to comply with FAIR and CARE data principles
- Provide clear guidance to researchers on what to store, when, and for how long
- Integrate Australian investments in digital research infrastructure into their international context

¹⁵ Towards Coordinated International Support of Core Data Resources for the Life Science, W. Anderson, et al.. bioRxiv 110825; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/110825>